

SCIENTIFIC PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF PROBLEMS OF THINKING DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

thinking develops while solving creative problems. Ways to find a solution to the problem are sought, such as a new solution. The independent creative process requires constant research and consistency.

Key words

thinking, national value, cognition, creative matter, mind, personality, qualities of will, behavior, activity, spiritual experience.

Thinking is a measure of mental maturity that governs the entire life and creative activity of a person.

After we gained independence, the people's outlook changed, they began to realize their identity. Because our national values have been restored. Through thinking, a person acquires his own independent opinion in the process of social relations and can convey his existing knowledge to others.

In the psychological literature, scientifically based opinions are expressed about thinking and its development. Including; tasks to be carried out by the teacher and creative problems that develop students' thinking are given.

In terms of cognitive processes, such points as solving mathematical problems, mastering grammatical categories and familiarizing with complex drawings play an important role in the formation of theoretical thinking in students. Proper development of the process of writing a dictation, statement or essay to students plays an important role in the formation of practical thinking.

1. In order to develop thinking and its independence, it is necessary to systematically organize problematic lessons on the main important topic, which stimulate the student's thinking, not being limited to the knowledge available in memory. It is necessary to organize the lessons, taking into account that the needs and interests of knowledge are important conditions for thinking.

2. In the process of conducting classes, it is necessary to properly organize questions from students and pay special attention. The question should help the student to develop answers, defend his point of view. It is necessary to pay great attention to the development of speech, because speech and thinking are related to each other.

3. Dialogic education should be contrasted with monologic education of students. In practice, thinking develops only in a dialogical situation. It is necessary to keep in mind that having complete information about the problem being discussed in the partnership will create an opportunity for correct discussion in this or that discussion.

4. Education, which is a type of activity, should be introduced into the practice of more favorable situations, consideration of the answer, and teaching methods that offer management of the situation. Otherwise, there is a risk of formation of signs of an ineffective method of thinking, such as ignoring the opposition to the "latency" nature of the objects, inability to draw clear conclusions and generalizations independently. The more situations the teacher examines with the students while explaining the topic, the better the student will master the topic.

5. The teacher should not blindly use the "trial and error" method in educational practice, but should pay attention to the students' search for different patterns.

6. Students should be frequently asked questions that require understanding of the characters explained and shown.

7. In the organization of lessons, the main attention should be paid not to their appearance, but to the content and attractiveness of the lessons, their implementation. During the lesson, the teacher should pay more attention to the success and achievements of the students.

8. It is necessary to give students more creative tasks, to develop their skills with various "disturbing" materials.

9. During the lesson, the pedagogue should give "quantitative" indicators to the students in the process of performing complex tasks, so that these instructions should not limit the thinking of the students.

Mental qualities and individual learning characteristics are formed in educational activities during adolescence in terms of development. That higher nervous activity is analytical-synthetic in nature; I.P. Pavlov repeatedly emphasized that analysis and synthesis are conflicting and at the same time interconnected processes. Both boys and girls have analytical intelligence and synthetic intelligence. Manifestors of analytical mind divide each rule into its

components in order to master the rules of general science, look for evidence, examples and are satisfied only after proving the truth of a particular rule. Manifestors of synthetic intelligence cling to evidence and examples, quickly, and sometimes hastily, synthesize them and generalize them. Manifestations of synthetic intelligence "understand" what the teacher is trying to say, or what the author is trying to say when reading a book, as if jumping ahead in the presentation of new material.

According to their age, some teenagers' minds are more influenced by feelings, while others are dominated by the logic of facts. These features are evident in the process of writing an independent essay: young men and women who are influenced by feelings express the social and especially personal evaluation of the works rather than stating the facts; boys and girls who follow the logic of facts are based on facts and rarely state their own facts and give arguments showing the social importance of a particular writer and his works. Adolescent boys and girls differ in terms of the breadth of their intelligence: some learn a lot of facts and deeply understand the basic laws of science, while others differ in the narrowness of their level of assimilation of facts. But he understands the rules deeply, he is content with reading the third ones superficially, understanding and memorizing them. Great differences are visible in speech culture: usually, many young men and women have rich speech, they are able to vividly and figuratively imagine the event clearly and deeply.

The emergence and consolidation of these individual characteristics of the mind depends on many reasons. Adolescents imitate older family members and teachers, especially those they love and respect, willingly or often involuntarily imitating their behavior and speech. In youth, this imitation can create stable forms of mental activity. Achievements and incentives in learning specific subjects can reinforce the way learning material is remembered and recalled.

Educating a person is a delicate, internal conflicting process that requires a lot of attention. Therefore, it is necessary to observe the ways in which the personality of a growing person is being formed with great interest and meticulousness characteristic of scientists. The teacher should not rely only on his own problem and intuition. It is necessary to know it well in order to manage the pedagogical process. In the work of education, one of the main tasks of personality development is performed, or the generation is given knowledge gained in human experience, in which the necessary life skills and abilities are formed. In the educational process, the student receives knowledge that gives him the opportunity to participate in his general work and improve important social production.

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